

UKBOL Standard Operating Procedure: Autonorm-indexing with iconPCR

Version 1, January 2026, Alyssa Paul

iconPCR guide:

- Use only authorized consumables with this machine or it will break!
- SYBR green (e.g. Thermofisher 10 000x) should be added at a final concentration of 0.5x to indexing reaction.
- Take note of colours of the LED display on the machine. If it flashes Yellow/Red at any point you must contact n6support.

LED display

High Level	Color	Name	Description
Good	Blue	Idle	Instrument is not operating and ready to accept work
	Flashing Blue	On hold	Instrument is holding samples at a set temperature indefinitely (generally after completing thermal cycling)
	Green	Running experiment	Experiment is running (not yet at final hold)
	Flashing Green	Starting experiment	Experiment is starting (warming heated lid, sending recipe)
Abnormal	Yellow	Warning while running	Fault detected during run but run is proceeding, contact support
	Flashing Yellow	Warning while Idle	Instrument is not running, but potential issue detected during previous run or at idle state, contact support
	Red	Run Aborted	Experiment ended unexpectedly, generally can restart run but contact support if error persists
	Flashing Red	Fault	Hardware fault, instrument inoperable, contact support
Reduced Functionality	Purple	Simulation Mode	Shipping mode or simulation program (controlled by technical support)

Login details:

Computer password = **iconpcr**

N6 Software: User = **Admin**; password = **n6tecadmin**

N6 Data Analysis: Can be found on the computer or online: <https://analysis.n6tec.com/>

Login details are the same for the app or link: User = **guest**; password = **iconPCR**

Equipment required:

- iconPCR
- iDOT LT (optional)
- Integra VIAFLOW (or equivalent)
- Liquidator 96-channel pipette (or equivalent)
- Sterile 200uL tips
- Sterile 20uL tips
- White low profile skirted plates
- qPCR seals (optically clear)
- qPCR seal applicator

Procedure:

Notes:

- Ensure you are using the correct concentration of SYBR green (1/100 vs 1/1000).
- SYBR green can only be freeze/thawed 3 times so use aliquots rather than stock.

Option 1 (SYBR added independent of Amplitaq):

Prepare plate in clean room.

Reagent	Volume (1 reaction)	Volume (100 reactions)	Equipment	Room
Amplitaq Gold 360 Master Mix	22.5 µL	2250 uL	Integra	Clean room
SYBR Green (1/1000)	2.5 µL	250 uL	iDOT	
20 µM combined i5/i7 index	5 µL		Integra	
Library	20 µL		Liquidator	Pre-PCR room
	50 µL			

1. Transfer each reagent in order (top to bottom) using specified equipment.
2. Seal with qPCR seal, ensuring a tight seal with the qPCR seal applicator.
3. Vortex and spin down twice.

Option 2 (SYBR added to Amplitaq):

Prepare plate in clean room.

1. Make a master mix of Amplitaq and SYBR Green, mix thoroughly and add to plate directly before using. Volumes for one plate below:

	1 plate
Amplitaq Gold 360 Master Mix	2437.8 µL
SYBR Green (1/100)	12.2 µL
	2450 µL

2. Add to plate using multichannel pipette.

3. Add the combined indexes and library to the plate following these volumes in order. Note the adapter ligated library must be added in the pre-PCR room as DNA is not allowed in the clean room.

Reagent	Volume (1 reaction)	Equipment	Room
Amplitaq Gold 360 + SYBR Green	25 µL	Integra	Clean room
20 µM combined i5/i7 index	5 µL	Integra	
Library	20 µL	Liquidator	Pre-PCR room
	50 µL		

4. Seal with qPCR seal, ensuring a tight seal with the qPCR seal applicator.
5. Vortex and spin down twice.

IconPCR setup

1. Login to software (note, can take around 5 mins for instrument to connect with laptop)
2. Choose 'open drawer' to add plate into machine, then 'close drawer'
3. Choose **SCR Indexing (AN+1)** option, save protocol as batch ID "UK_XXX" (say SAVE AS instead of SAVE), settings are as follows:
 - Autonom option:
 - Max 23 cycles
 - Min 5 cycles
 - RFU threshold 200
 - Additional Slope +1
4. Ensure the run conditions are:
 - 95°C for 10 minutes
 - Library specific number of the following cycle conditions:
 - 95°C for 30 seconds
 - 60°C for 30 seconds
 - 72°C for **60 seconds**
 - Final extension of 72°C for 7 minutes
5. Select all wells as 'unknown' in 'Plate view' then proceed with run. If you forget this step the machine will auto select all wells.
6. Runtime is approximately 2 hours.
7. After the run is finished, the light on machine will flash blue. Press 'end experiment', then export data (by COLUMN) and save the file to downloads.
8. Take samples out of iconPCR and store in fridge until further use.
9. Open data in the analysis app. and export 'Stop cycle & pooling vols'